

O - lineage

- ▲ ana_tur
- ▲ rem_arm
- ▲ cau_tur_geo
- ▲ cyp_cyp

C - lineage

- × car_svn_hrv
- × car_aut_hun
- × lig_ita
- + carp_rou_mda
- + rod_bgr
- × mac_mkd_grc
- × cec_grc
- × ada_grc

M - lineage

- ibe_esp_eus
- ibe_esp_north
- ibe_esp_south
- ibe_esp_westprt
- mel_dnk
- mel_irl
- mel_rus
- mel_che
- mel_imn
- rut_mlt (A - lineage)